

DEVELOPMENT OF PICTURE STORY BOOK LEARNING MEDIA TO INCREASE ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS' INTEREST IN READING ENGLISH

Marhamah ¹

¹ Universitas Islam Riau, Indonesia

*Corresponding Address: marhamah@edu.uir.ac.id

Received: 22 October 2022 | Approved: 21 November 2022 | Published: 29 December 2022

Abstract: This study aimed to develop a picture storybook learning media to increase interest in reading English for elementary school students in grade 5 SDN Pekanbaru Riau. This study uses research and development methods (Research and Development). This research will produce learning tools in the form of learning media, which will be tested for validity and practicality. The steps in developing picture storybooks for learning to read follow the 4-D model (Define, Design, Development, Disseminate). The test subjects in this research and development were class V students at SDN Pekanbaru Riau. This research and development trial was conducted on a small group of 5 students. The type of data taken in this research is qualitative and quantitative data. At the product validation stage, the data obtained is qualitative in the form of responses and comments from student interviews after using the media, as well as input, criticism, and suggestions from validators and teachers in improving picture storybooks. Furthermore, quantitative data is obtained from statements in providing assessments of media products during validation by media, material, and language validators, and teacher response questionnaire assessments. After the data is obtained, the next step is to analyze the data. The data that will be obtained in this research is quantitative and qualitative. Quantitative data was obtained from media, material and language validation sheets, and teacher response questionnaires. Furthermore, qualitative data was obtained from student interviews and input from validators and teachers. Responses, suggestions, and validator input are considered and analyzed to improve the product. The results of this research are the result of expert validation of picture storybook learning media material of 81%. They are included in the 80-100% interval so that they are included in the high category and are very suitable for use. The results of this study are the results of expert validation of picture storybook learning media material as much as 81 % and belonging to the 80-100% interval so that it is included in the high category and is very feasible to use. The results of the validation from media experts on the development of picture storybook learning media to increase interest in reading for grade 5 SDN students are in the high category with the eligibility of 78% from 3 aspects. The validated aspects included the suitability of the presentation with the demands of student-centered learning, the way of presentation, readability, and communicativeness. The suitability of the presentation with the demands of student-centered learning has a feasibility of 68%, which is in the high category.

Keywords: Development, Learning Media, Increasing Interest, English

INTRODUCTION

The learning process involves the interaction of teachers and students. Learning is an activity used to generate initiative and the role of students in implementing a curriculum that has been agreed upon by an educational institution so that students can achieve educational goals (Apriliani & Radia, 2020). Learning objectives, learning materials, learning methodology, and learning assessments have been adjusted by the teacher so that everything can fit into the learning environment. Learning methods and media are very prominent aspects of learning methodology, both of which have an important position in achieving learning goals effectively (Masykur, Nofrizal & Syazali, 2017).

At this time, students are faced with the problem of overcoming time constraints and being able to read in a relatively short time but can obtain as much information as possible (Rahmania, Miarsyah, & Sartono, 2015). How to do reading activities effectively without wasting time. In line with this statement, it appears that reading literacy skills are needed by students in line with the rapid development of information and technology today. Hanggi (2016) states that reading literacy can be a means for students to recognize, understand, and apply the knowledge they get at school. Basic literacy, including reading literacy, should be instilled in elementary education (Ristanto, Zubaidah, Amin & Rochman, 2017). This is necessary to improve students' ability to access information or knowledge. Literacy will lead students to understand a message (Hernowo, 2003). The Ministry of Education and Culture (2016) also conveys the importance of literacy, which states that a culture of literacy embedded in students affects the level of success and the ability of students to understand information analytically, critically, and reflectively. The government has also launched the National Literacy Movement (GLB) program, which aims to foster children's character through a culture of literacy (reading and writing) (Tarigan, 2018).

So far, the paradigm and general perception inherent among educators is that making teaching materials is a difficult and stressful job. This job wastes a lot of time and effort (Ratnasari, E. M., & Zubaidah, E. 2019). Sometimes, you must sacrifice your leisure time by sitting in front of a computer screen or working with various materials to create innovative teaching materials. These are all wrong perceptions and must be corrected (Fazalani & Fatimah, 2022).

Teaching and learning activities can be carried out in various ways, such as lectures. Still, the lecture method's learning process is less effective because students sit quietly, listening to the teacher's explanation (Handayani, Fazalani, Mayanti, & Pertiwi, 2023). The learning process can be effective if teachers and students actively participate in learning activities. Teachers can require students to be actively involved in learning by using learning media (Sumantri, M., Sudana, D. N., & Yoni Adnyana P, I. B. E. 2017).

In line with the demands of elementary school education, which lead to learning with contextual concepts, teachers are expected to be able to present learning that can be related to everyday life. Picture storybook media will encourage students' interest in reading and high curiosity about the subject matter to be conveyed (Hidayati & Astuti, 2020). Students can be interested in books that contain light stories from everyday life and interesting pictures. Combining pictures and writing adapted to the material and arranged interestingly will make students not feel bored reading (Sunarti, S. 2018).

Picture storybooks can attract attention because their appearance is very popular among children. Picture storybooks have a function that can be used as a decoration and support in stories that can help facilitate the process of understanding the book's contents. A storybook with pictures is a unified story accompanied by pictures. Through picture story books, it is hoped that readers can easily receive information and descriptions of the stories that will be conveyed (Nugraheni, I., Harsiati, T., & Qohar, A. 2019). Thus, picture storybooks can be classified as appropriate for teaching and learning for low-grade students (Nurjanah & Hakim, 2018).

Children at elementary school age are in the concrete operational stage. This shows that children like concrete or real objects. In addition, children also have very high fantasy power. To make it more interesting and motivate children to do something, media is needed to channel creative imagination to children, one of which is picture story books. Picture storybooks can help make it easier for children to translate ideas into language because pictures inspire and motivate students to learn, especially in teaching reading. If difficulties in learning a language, especially learning to read, are left alone without any follow-up, it will result in many students experiencing difficulties in reading. The illustrations in picture storybooks make it easy for children to remember and understand (Ratnasari & Zubaidah, 2019).

Picture storybooks are stories made into books and contain pictures to represent intertwined and related stories. Interesting learning media can increase students' attention to material, and initial responses to the learning process through media images can strengthen children's memories and facilitate children's understanding of story content (Afnida, Fakhriah & Fitriani, 2016).

Picture storybook media will encourage students' interest in reading and a high curiosity about the subject that will be delivered, especially in English. Students can be interested in books that contain light stories from everyday life and interesting pictures. Combining pictures and writing adapted to the material and arranged interestingly will make students not feel bored reading.

The first step taken by the researchers was observation at public elementary schools in Riau. After observing, the researcher tried to interview one of the teachers at the school to get some

problems regarding children's lack of interest in reading and the obstacles to children's lack of interest in reading in English. One of the inhibiting factors is the lack of learning media; schools must facilitate learning media in the form of picture books to attract students' interest in reading, especially in English reading.

Interest in reading is a desire that arises when someone tries to read. People with a strong desire to read will manifest in their willingness to get reading material and then read it on their own accord or outside encouragement. Interest in reading is a strong desire accompanied by one's efforts to read (Gusmayanti, Fauziah & Muhdiyati, 2018).

Generating intention is the main key so that children like to read. The second theory is that interest in reading is a will. When reading something, it should be based on a will or desire. The desire which then drives to do something without coercion. The third theory is that interest in reading is a preference. Interest is also related to likes. The feeling of liking reading will be a factor in increasing interest in reading. Likes can be interpreted as not being bored with the activities (Suantara, Suarjana & Sudana, 2019).

Based on the explanation above, the researcher will develop a research product on learning media for picture storybooks to increase students' interest in reading English SDN Pekanbaru, Riau. The development of this learning media offers several advantages, including story books packaged in a story of everyday life, which makes it easier for students to read and easily tell them. This media was created to help students improve their English reading while learning to memorize English vocabulary. In its use, students are invited to learn through various daily activities outlined in picture storybooks. Through this media, it is hoped that students can more easily understand the material, memorize vocabulary, and help deal with various problems later in real life when English is currently the second language in the world.

METHODS

This research uses research and development methods (Arief S. Sadiman et al. 2012). This research will produce learning tools in the form of learning media, which will be tested for validity and practicality. The steps in developing picture storybooks for learning to read were followed by the 4-D model (Define, Design, Development, Disseminate), modified from the Thiagarajan development model (Trianto, 2014). The test subjects in this research and development were class V students at SDN Pekanbaru Riau. This research and development trial was conducted on a small group of 5 students. The type of data taken in this research is qualitative and quantitative data. At the product

validation stage, the data obtained is qualitative in responses and comments from student interviews after using the media and input, criticism, and suggestions from validators and teachers in improving picture storybooks. Furthermore, quantitative data is obtained from statements in providing assessments of media products during validation by media, material, and language validators, and teacher response questionnaire assessments. After the data is obtained, the next step is to analyze the data. The data that will be obtained in this research is quantitative and qualitative. Quantitative data was obtained from media, material, language validation sheets, and teacher response questionnaires. Furthermore, qualitative data was obtained from student interviews and input from validators and teachers. Responses, suggestions, and validator input are considered and analyzed to improve the product.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

This research produces a product in the form of a picture storybook for learning to read in class V SDN, which includes validity and practicality. This learning media consists of the cover, book contents, and cover.

The development of picture storybooks for learning to read in class V SDN uses the 4-D model stages. The 4-D development model consists of four stages, namely the definition stage, design stage, development stage, and dissemination stage. The research process that has been carried out shows the procedure for developing picture storybooks for learning to read in class V at SDN Pekanbaru Riau.

Based on assessing the validity and practicality of picture storybooks, the media has met the eligibility standards; namely, the media is declared valid and practical. In this case, the storybook has met the validity category, as proven by assessments by media, material, and language validators.

Figure 1. Cover Design

At this stage, after making a picture storybook design, testing material experts, learning media experts, and learning design experts, the researcher gets suggestions and comments for improving the

picture storybook learning media after revising the picture storybook media according to the suggestions given.

The following are the results of the validation test from the three experts. The results of the expert validation of the picture book learning media material were as much as 81 %. They belonged to the 80-100% interval, so they were included in the high category and were very feasible to use.

Aspect	Ideal Score	Actual Score	percentage	Category
C	30	26	96%	Tall
A	15	15	100%	Very high
D	12	20	80%	Tall
The average material expert validation results			81%	Tall

Table 1 shows that the results of the validation of material experts on the development of picture storybook learning media to increase interest in reading English for grade 5 SDN students are in the high category with eligibility of 81% of 3 aspects. Validated aspects include relevance, accuracy, and language suitability with good and correct language rules.

The relevant aspect has an ideal score of 30 while the actual score is 26 with a percentage of 96%, so it is in the high category and deserves to be followed up. Furthermore, the aspect of accuracy has an ideal score of 15 while the actual score is 15, so the percentage is 100% with a very high category. The language suitability aspect has an ideal score of 12 and an actual score of 20 with a percentage of 80%, with the 80% category having a high category.

The results of the validation of learning media experts by one of the lecturers from FKIP, FKES obtained an eligibility of 78% and was classified in the 70% -100% interval, so it was included in the high category. The average percentage of eligibility results and media expert validation.

Aspect	Ideal Score	Actual Score	percentage	Category
A	13	12	68%	tall
B	30	35	75%	tall
C	12	20	70%	Tall
The average material expert validation results			78%	Tall

The results of the validation from media experts on the development of picture storybook learning media to increase interest in reading for grade 5 SDN students are in the high category with the eligibility of 78% from 3 aspects. The Aspe-validated aspects included the suitability of the presentation with the demands of student-centered learning, the way of presentation and readability, ty, and communicativeness. The aspect of suif the presentation with the demands of student-centered learning has a feasibility of 68% which is in the high category. One indicator scored very well, namely

encouraging students to practice the story's contents; 1 indicator received a good value, namely encouraging students' curiosity about the story's contents, and one indicator scored less well, namely encouraging student interaction with learning resources.

The results of the preliminary study found that the problem was the limitations of learning media and the use of unattractive learning media. This can result in students not understanding the material presented, making students less enthusiastic and easily bored when asked to read, so student learning outcomes are not good.

The development stage carried out was validating the media and conducting limited trials. A team of media, material, and language validators carries out validation. Furthermore, the media that has been validated will undergo a limited trial. Asyhar (2012: 100) believes that "this is necessary because sometimes what is conceptualized by writers and experts is not necessarily by the reality on the ground." After being tested on students, students' suggestions and comments are needed to revise the product. Apart from students, teachers are also observers of learning because the media is intended and used by teachers.

The distribution stage is carried out after the picture storybook is declared valid and practical. Research and development of picture storybooks during the dissemination process is used in other classes. Thiagarajan et al. (1974:9) stated, "The dissemination stage is carried out to promote the development product so that it can be accepted by users, whether individuals, a group, or a system." The classes used for distribution were class V students at SDN Pekanbaru Riau. In this case, picture storybooks aim to promote media and introduce media. So, in the future, it is hoped that media can be further developed for learning to read or other learning in elementary schools.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the explanation above, it can be concluded that a learning media product produced is a picture storybook for English. This learning media contains English subjects for grade 5 SDN in Pekanbaru Riau. The results of the expert validation of the picture book learning media material were as much as 81 %. They belonged to the 80-100% interval, so they were included in the high category and were very feasible to use. The results of the validation from media experts on the development of picture storybook learning media to increase interest in reading for grade 5 SDN students are in the high category with the eligibility of 78% from 3 aspects. The validated aspects included the suitability of the presentation with the demands of student-centered learning, the way of

presentation, and readability and communicativeness. The suitability of the presentation with the demands of student-centered learning has a feasibility of 68%, which is in the high category.

REFERENCES

- Afnida , Fakhriah, & Fitriani. (2016). Penggunaan Buku Cerita Bergambar dalam Pengembangan Bahasa Anak. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 53-54.
- Al-Tabany, Trianto Ibnu B. (2014). *Mendesain Model Pembelajaran Inovatif, Progresif dan Kontekstual*. Jakarta: Kencana.
- Apriliani & Radia, (2020). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Buku Cerita Bergambar untuk Meningkatkan Minat Membaca Siswa Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu Volume 4 Nomor 4*. 994 – 1003.
- Asyhar, R. (2012). *Kreatif mengembangkan media pembelajaran*. Jakarta: Gaung Persada (GP) Press Jakarta.
- Fazalani & Fathimah , (2022). Upaya Peningkatan Kognitif Anak Dengan Media Bahan Alam Sekitar Pada Anak Paud Di Praya Lombok Tengah . *Lingua Franca: Jurnal Bahasa, Sastra, dan Pengajarannya* . Jilid 6. No 1.
- Gusmayanti , W., Fauziah, RSP, & Muhdiyati , I. (2018). Pengaruh Minat Membaca Cerita Pahlawan pada Hasil Pengajaran . *Didaktika Tauhidi : Jurnal Pendidikan Guru Sekolah Dasar*, 5(2), 123-134.
- Handayani, Fazalani, Mayanti, & Pertiwi, (2023). Penerapan Metode Inquiri Dalam Meningkatkan Kemampuan Menulis Teks Eksplanasi SDN Nurul Jihat Desa Pemepek. *NUSRA: Jurnal Penelitian dan Ilmu Pendidikan*. Vol 4. No 3.
- Hernowo . 2003. *Quantum Reading: Cara Cepat dan Bermanfaat untuk Merangsang Munculnya Potensi Membaca* . Bandung: MLC.
- Hidayati & Astuti, (2020). Pengembangan Bukatber (Buku Kata Bergambar) Berbasis Android Untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Menulis. *Journal for Lesson and Learning Studies* Vol. 3 No.2. 153-164.
- Kemendikbud. (2016). *Permendikbud No. 23 tahun 2016 Tentang Standar Penilaian Pendidikan*. Jakarta: Kementerian Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan.

- Masykur, Nofrizal, dan Syazali. (2017). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Matematika dengan Macromedia Flash. *Al-Jabar: Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika*. Universitas Islam Negeri Raden Intan Lampung : P- ISSN 2086-5872, e-ISSN 2540-7562, Vol. 8, No. 2, 2017, Hal 177 – 186
- Nagasaputra , Hanggi. (2016). Studi Kasus Mengenai Gambaran Lima Dimensi Religiusitas pada Dewasa Awal Pelaku Hubungan Seksual Pranikah di Kota Bandung. Skripsi. Bandung: Fakultas Psikologi Universitas Maranatha.
- Nugraheni, I., Harsiati, T., & Qohar, A. (2019). Media Buku Cerita untuk Meningkatkan Kemampuan Membaca dan Menulis Siswa Kelas IV Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Pendidikan: Teori, Penelitian Dan Pengembangan*, 4(3), 322–328.
- Nurjanah, Siti. 2018. “ Perkembangan Nilai Agama Moral (STTPA TERCAPAI)”. *Jurnal Nasional*. Universitas Islam Negeri Kalijaga Jogja.
- Rahmania , S., Miarsyah , M. & Sartono , N. (2015) . Perbedaan Kemampuan Literasi Sains Siswa dengan Gaya Kognitif Bidang Independen dan Bidang Dependent . *Biosfer Jurnal Tadris Pendidikan Biologi* Vol 8 (2) .
- Ratnasari & Zubaidah . (2019). Pengaruh Penggunaan Buku Cerita Bergambar Terhadap Kemampuan Berbicara Anak. *Scholaria : Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan*. 9(3) 267-275.
- Ratnasari & Zubaidah,(2019). Pengaruh Penggunaan Buku Cerita Bergambar Terhadap Kemampuan Berbicara Anak . *Scholaria: Jurnal Pendidikan dan Kebudayaan*, Vol. 9 No. 3. 267-275.
- Ratnasari, E. M., & Zubaidah, E. (2019). Pengaruh Penggunaan Buku Cerita Bergambar Terhadap Kemampuan Berbicara Anak. *Scholaria: Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Kebudayaan*, 9(3), 270. <https://doi.org/10.24246/j.js.2019.v9.i3.p267-275>.
- Rubhan Masykur , Nofrizal , Muhamad Syazali , (2017) . Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran Matematika dengan Macromedia Flash. *Jurnal Pendidikan Matematika* Vol. 8 No. 2 hal . 177-186.
- Suantara , IK, Suarjana , IM , & Sudana , DN (2019). Kecenderungan Minat Membaca Siswa Kelas V SD Negeri 5 Seraya Barat Kecamatan Karangasem. 44–46.
- Sugiyono. 2011. *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif Kualitatif dan R&D*. Bandung : Alfabeta.
- Sukmadinata , Nana Syaodih . 2010. *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan*. Bandung: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya.

Sumantri, M., Sudana, D. N., & Yoni Adnyana P, I. B. E. (2017). Penerapan Media Gambar Dan Kartu Huruf Untuk Meningkatkan Keterampilan Membaca Permulaan. *International Journal of Elementary Education*, 1(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.23887/ijee.v1i1.11433>.

Sunarti, S. (2018). Upaya Peningkatan Motivasi dan Kemampuan Membaca Permulaan Melalui Media Kartu Huruf Pada Siswa Kelas 1 SD Negeri 1 Pakis Kecamatan Kradenan Tahun Pelajaran 2017/2018. *EFEKTOR*. <https://doi.org/10.29407/e.v5i1.11945>.

Tarigan, (2018). Pengembangan Buku Cerita Bergambar Untuk Meningkatkan Minat Baca Siswa Kelas Iv Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Curere*. Vol.02. No. 02. 141-152.

Thiagarajan, Sivasailam dkk. (1974). "Instructional Development For Training Teachers Of Exceptional Children A Sourcebook, Minnesota: University Of Minnesota.

Arief S. Sadiman,dkk. (2012). *Media Pendidikan (Pengertian, Pengembangan, Dan Pemanfaatannya)*. Jakarta: Grafindo Persada.